

How to find an Active Journal indexed in Scopus that adopt the Arabic Language (Updating List September 2023)

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Abstract:

This paper is a data-paper aims to help researchers who want to publish in Arabic Language by simplifying the search process for Active journals indexed in Scopus that adopt the Arabic Language. Moreover, it aims to contribute to increase of Universities 's visibility by increasing citations of research published in Arabic especially in subject of Social science and subject of Economics, Econometrics, and Finance.

We have arranged these Active journals indexed in Scopus that adopt the Arabic Language into one brief file, and we have also added: Ranking journals by quartiles; Direct links to Home page of Journals; Links to Journals Home-pages in the Scopus Preview.

Keywords: *Arabic Language; Data-paper; Journals indexed in Scopus.*

JEL Classification Codes: Y10; Y90.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Although there are a lot of research in Arabic, and there are many people interested in publishing in Arabic, there is a problem with the lack of journals indexed in Scopus that adopt the Arabic Language. For that, Many researchers face the problem of publishing in Arabic in indexed journals, which requires facilitating the process of searching for journals that adopt the Arabic Language, determines the specializations or areas accepted in each journal. Through this paper we want to provide a brief-tables with links about journals indexed in Scopus that adopt the Arabic Language.

Regarding list of journals Indexed in Scopus that adopt the Arabic Language (Updating List May 2023) It was previously published by (Benziane, 2023), But that work included only the list and did not include any additions, While our work more updating based on Scopus (Scopus, 2023), and includes classifying journals, providing direct links, as well as Quartile ranking journals to facilitating and simplifying the search process for Active journals indexed in Scopus that adopt the Arabic Language.

2. Objectives of the Paper

This paper aims to:

- Help researchers who want to publish in Arabic language by simplifying the search process for Active journals indexed in Scopus that adopt the Arabic Language.
- Contributes to increase of Universities 's visibility by increases citations of research published in Arabic
- Increases Arabic research published in journals indexed, especially in subject of Social science and Economics, Econometrics, and Finance.

3. Method

At first, we used Scopus source list (Updating List September 2023), and we tried to classified for helping researchers to find any journal from those 29 in easy way. Secondly; We have created Abbreviations to make tables contain all the important information. Thirdly; we searched for: Direct links to Home page of all Journals; Links to Journals Home-pages in the Scopus Preview.

Table N°1 : Active journals indexed in Scopus that adopt Arabic

N	Source record ID	Source Title (Medline-sourced journals are indicated in Green)	Print-ISSN	E-ISSN	Act / Inact	Lang	OAS	May 2023	S T	Publisher's Name
1	21100322122	Al-Jami'ah	0126012X	2338557X	Act	ENG, ARA			J	UIN Sunan Kalijaga
2	21101052922	Arab Journal of Forensic Sciences and Forensic Medicine	16586786	16586794	Act	ARA, ENG	UOA		J	Naif University Publishing House
3	21100819201	Arab Journal of Plant Protection	0255982X	24125407	Act	ARA			J	Arab Society for Plant Protection
4	21100840337	Baghdad Science Journal	20788665	24117986	Act	ARA	UOA		J	University of Baghdad
5	21100455924	Brill Studies in Middle Eastern Literatures	15715183		Act	ENG, ARA			B S	Brill Academic Publishers
6	5600153254	Dirasat: Human and Social Sciences	10263721	26636190	Act	ENG, ARA			J	University of Jordan
7	20214	Eastern Mediterranean Health Journal	10203397		Act	ARA, FRE, ENG			J	World Health Organization
8	21100324067	Global Journal Al-Thaqafah	22320474	22320482	Act	ENG, MAY, ARA	UOA		J	Universiti Sultan Azlan Shah
9	21100426624	Handbook of Oriental Studies. Section 1, The Near and Middle East	01699423		Act	ARA, ENG, GER			B S	Brill
10	21100809798	Iraqi Journal of Agricultural Sciences	00750530	24100862	Act	ARA, ENG	UOA		J	University of Baghdad, College of Agriculture
11	19500157815	Iraqi Journal of Veterinary Sciences	16073894	16073894	Act	ARA, ENG	UOA		J	University of Mosul
12	21101141752	Iraqi National Journal of Earth Science	16823222	26642816	Act	ARA;ENG	UOA	Ad d	J	University of Mosul College of Science
13	21101101951	Islam Tetkikleri Dergisi		27176967	Act	ARA;ENG;TUR	UOA		J	Istanbul University Press
14	21100407919	Islamic History and Civilization	09292403		Act	ARA, GER, FRE, ENG			B S	Brill
15	21101042995	Jordan Journal for History and	19969546		Act	ARA			J	Deanship of Academic

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		Archaeology								Research, The University of Jordan
16	21100403909	Journal of Islamic Manuscripts	18784631	1878464X	Act	ENG, ARA, FRE			J	Brill
17	19700174646	Journal of King Abdulaziz University, Islamic Economics	10187383	16584244	Act	ENG, ARA			J	King Abdulaziz University Scientific Publishing Center
18	21100211116	Journal of Qur'anic Studies	14653591	17551730	Act	ENG, ARA			J	Edinburgh University Press
19	21101107566	Jurnal Ilmiah Islam Futura	14121190	24077542	Act	ARA;E NG;IN D	UOA	Ad d	J	Universitas Islam Negeri Ar-Raniry
20	21101132408	Kufa Journal for Agricultural Sciences	20727798	23128186	Act	ARA;E NG		Ad d	J	University of Kufa
21	21100407217	Mnemosyne, Supplements	01698958		Act	ARA, ENG, FRE, GRE			B S	Brill Academic Publishers
22	21100253111	Parole de l'Orient	02588331		Act	ENG, FRE, ARA			J	University Saint-Esprit
23	21100407421	Philosophia Antiqua	00791687		Act	GER, FRE, ARM, ENG, GRE			B S	Brill Academic Publishers
24	19700187504	Scientific Journal of King Faisal University	16580311		Act	ARA, ENG			J	King Faisal University
25	21100407605	Studia Islamika	02150492	23556145	Act	ENG, ARA			J	Gedung Pusat Pengkajian Islam dan Masyarakat UIN Jakarta
26	21100406932	Studies in the History and Society of the Maghrib	18779808		Act	ENG, FRE, ARA			B S	Brill
27	21100406946	Texts and Studies on the Qur'an	15672808		Act	FRE, ARA, GER, ENG			B S	Brill
28	21101118628	Tikrit Journal of Engineering Sciences	1813162X	23127589	Act	ARA;E NG	UOA	Ad d	J	Tikrit University
29	21101121509	Ulumuna	14113457	23557648	Act	ARA;E NG;IN D	UOA	Ad d	J	Universitas Islam Negeri (UIN) Mataram

Source : (Scopus, 2023); (MEDDAH, 2023)

Table N°2 : Abbreviations in Table N°1

Abbreviations	Meaning
Act or Inact	Active/ InActive
Act	Active
Inact	InActive
Lang	Article language in source (three-letter ISO language codes)
ENG	ENGLISH
ARA	ARABIC
FRE	FRENCH
OAS	Open Access status
UOA	Unpaywall Open Access
ST	Source Type
J	Journal
BS	Book Series

Source : (MEDDAH, 2023)

Table N°3 : Active journals indexed in Scopus that adopt Arabic by Subject

3400Vet				
3300SS		SS		
3100P&A				P&A
3000PTP		PTP		
2700Med		Med		
2600Math				Math
2300ES			ES	
2200Enrg				
2000EEF				
1900EPS				
1700CS				CS
1600C				Ch
1500CE				
1300BGMB				BGMB
1200ArtSH	ArtSH			
1100ABS				ABS
1000G				
TL:HS				
TL:PS				PS
TL:SS	TSS	TSS		
TL:LS		LS	LS	LS
N	1	2	3	4

Table N°4: Number of Active journals indexed in Scopus that adopt Arabic by Subjects and its Abbreviations

Abbreviations	Subject	N
TL	Top level	-
LS	Life Sciences	6
TSS	TOP Social Sciences	20
PS	Physical Sciences	04
HS	Health Sciences	03
G	General	01
ABS	Agricultural and Biological Sciences	04
ArtsH	Arts and Humanities	17
BGMB	Biochemistry, Genetics and Molecular Biology	01
CE	Chemical Engineering	01
Ch	Chemistry	01
CS	Computer Science	01
EPS	Earth and Planetary Sciences	01
EEF	Economics, Econometrics and Finance	01
Enrg	Engineering	01
ES	Environmental Science	03
Math	Mathematics	01
Med	Medicine	02
PTP	Pharmacology, Toxicology and Pharmaceutics	01
P&A	Physics and Astronomy	01
SS	Social Sciences	11
Vet	Veterinary	02

Source : (MEDDAH, 2023)

Table N°5: Active Journals indexed in Scopus that adopt Arabic (Quartile Ranking; Direct links of Journal's home-page)

N	Source Title (Medline-sourced journals are indicated in Green)	Quartile	Links
1	Al-Jami'ah	Q1	https://aljamiah.or.id/index.php/AJIS
2	Arab Journal of Forensic Sciences and Forensic Medicine	Q4	https://journals.nauss.edu.sa/index.php/AJFSFM/index
3	Arab Journal of Plant Protection	Q4	https://arabjournalpp.org/
4	Baghdad Science Journal	Q3	https://bsj.uobaghdad.edu.iq/index.php/BSJ
5	Brill Studies in Middle Eastern Literatures	Q2	https://brill.com/display/serial/BSME?language=en
6	Dirasat: Human and Social Sciences	Q3	https://dsr.ju.edu.jo/djournals/index.php/Hum
7	Eastern Mediterranean Health Journal	Q3	https://www2.cloud.editorialmanager.com/emhj/default2.aspx
			https://www.emro.who.int/emh-journal/eastern-mediterranean-health-journal/about-the-journal.html
8	Global Journal Al-Thaqafah	Q3	http://www.gjat.my/
9	Handbook of Oriental Studies. Section 1, The Near and Middle East	Q3	https://brill.com/display/serial/HO1?language=en
10	Iraqi Journal of Agricultural Sciences	Q2	https://jcoagri.uobaghdad.edu.iq/index.php/intro
11	Iraqi Journal of Veterinary Sciences	Q2	https://www.vetmedmosul.com/
12	Iraqi National Journal of Earth Science		https://earth.mosuljournals.com/
13	Islam Tetkikleri Dergisi	Q2	https://dergipark.org.tr/en/pub/iuislamtd
14	Islamic History and Civilization	Q2	https://brill.com/display/serial/IHC?language=en
15	Jordan Journal for History and Archaeology	Q3	https://journals.ju.edu.jo/ijha
16	Journal of Islamic Manuscripts	Q2	https://brill.com/view/journals/jim/jim-overview.xml
17	Journal of King Abdulaziz	Q4	https://journals.kau.edu.sa/index.php/J

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	University, Islamic Economics		KAUIE
18	Journal of Qur'anic Studies	Q2	https://www.eupublishing.com/loi/JQS
19	Jurnal Ilmiah Islam Futura		https://jurnal.ar-raniry.ac.id/index.php/islamfutura
20	Kufa Journal for Agricultural Sciences		https://journal.uokufa.edu.iq/index.php/kjas
21	Mnemosyne, Supplements	Q2	https://brill.com/view/serial/MNS
22	Parole de l'Orient	Q4	https://www.scopus.com/sourceid/21100253111
23	Philosophia Antiqua	Q2	https://brill.com/display/serial/PHA
24	Scientific Journal of King Faisal University	Q4	http://mportal.kfu.edu.sa/en/departments/sjournal/pages/desc.aspx
25	Studia Islamika	Q1	https://journal.uinjkt.ac.id/index.php/studia-islamika
26	Studies in the History and Society of the Maghrib		https://brill.com/display/serial/SHSM
27	Texts and Studies on the Qur'an		https://brill.com/display/serial/TSQ
28	Tikrit Journal of Engineering Sciences	Q3	https://tj-es.com/
29	Ulumuna (Indonesian Journal of Islam and Muslim Societies)		https://ulumuna.or.id/index.php/ujis

Source : (MEDDAH, 2023)

Table N°6: Active Journals indexed in Scopus that adopt Arabic (Links of Journals in the Scopus Preview)

N	Source Title (Medline-sourced journals are indicated in Green)	scimagojr.com / Scopus.com
1	Al-Jami'ah	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21100322122&tip=sid&clean=0
2	Arab Journal of Forensic Sciences and Forensic Medicine	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21101052922&tip=sid&clean=0
3	Arab Journal of Plant Protection	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21100819201&tip=sid&clean=0
4	Baghdad Science Journal	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21100840337&tip=sid&clean=0
5	Brill Studies in Middle Eastern Literatures	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21100455924&tip=sid&clean=0
6	Dirasat: Human and Social Sciences	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=5600153254&tip=sid&clean=0

7	Eastern Mediterranean Health Journal	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=20214&tip=sid&clean=0
8	Global Journal Al-Thaqafah	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21100324067&tip=sid&clean=0
9	Handbook of Oriental Studies. Section 1, The Near and Middle East	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21100426624&tip=sid&clean=0
10	Iraqi Journal of Agricultural Sciences	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21100809798&tip=sid&clean=0
11	Iraqi Journal of Veterinary Sciences	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=19500157815&tip=sid&clean=0
12	Iraqi National Journal of Earth Science	https://www.scopus.com/sourceid/21101141752?fbclid=IwAR0n4EpTz7oPqgyJ_T5ZDNhNjOPHvBRbDIkAqI7AJaXFXkV-WL5FsEENB-0
13	Islam Tetkikleri Dergisi	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21101101951&tip=sid&clean=0
14	Islamic History and Civilization	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21100407919&tip=sid&clean=0
15	Jordan Journal for History and Archaeology	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21101042995&tip=sid&clean=0
16	Journal of Islamic Manuscripts	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21100403909&tip=sid&clean=0
17	Journal of King Abdulaziz University, Islamic Economics	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=19700174646&tip=sid&clean=0
18	Journal of Qur'anic Studies	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21100211116&tip=sid&clean=0
19	Jurnal Ilmiah Islam Futura	https://www.scopus.com/sourceid/21101107566
20	Kufa Journal for Agricultural Sciences	https://www.scopus.com/sourceid/21101132408
21	Mnemosyne, Supplements	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21100407217&tip=sid&clean=0
22	Parole de l'Orient	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21100253111&tip=sid&clean=0
23	Philosophia Antiqua	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21100407421&tip=sid&clean=0
24	Scientific Journal of King Faisal University	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=19700187504&tip=sid&clean=0
25	Studia Islamika	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21100407605&tip=sid&clean=0
26	Studies in the History and Society of the Maghrib	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21100406932&tip=sid&clean=0
27	Texts and Studies on the Qur'an	https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21100406946&tip=sid&clean=0
28	Tikrit Journal of Engineering Sciences	https://www.scopus.com/sourceid/21101118628
29	Ulumuna (Indonesian Journal of Islam and Muslim Societies)	https://www.scopus.com/sourceid/21101121509

Source : (MEDDAH, 2023)

4. CONCLUSION

Through this Paper, we found that there are only 29 Active journals that accept publication in the Arabic language, and out of 29 journals, there are:

- Only two journals in the first quartile in the global ranking of journals;
- Only two journals concern about each following subject of;
 - ✓ Veterinary
 - ✓ Medicine
- Three journals concern about each following subject of;
 - ✓ Environmental Science
 - ✓ Health Sciences
- There is only one journal concern about each following subject of;
 - ✓ Biochemistry, Genetics and Molecular Biology;
 - ✓ Chemical Engineering; Chemistry;
 - ✓ Computer Science;
 - ✓ Earth and Planetary Sciences;
 - ✓ Economics, Econometrics and Finance;
 - ✓ Engineering;
 - ✓ Mathematics;
 - ✓ Pharmacology, Toxicology; and Pharmaceutics; and Physics and Astronomy.
- Four journals concern about Physical Sciences;
- Six journals concern about Life Sciences;
- Seventeen journals concern about Arts and Humanities;
- Twenty journals concern about Social Sciences.

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